

Change in the Microbial Flora Causing Neonatal Sepsis in Newborns Admitted in Tertiary Teaching Hospital in Jharkhand and the Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of the Recently Isolated Organisms.

Binita Nancy Khalkho¹, Simpal Shalini Minj², Seema Kumari³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College & Hospital, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Seema Kumari

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Abstract:

Neonatal sepsis is one of the commonest cause of morbidity and mortality in the neonatal nursery of any institution. The changing bacterial flora and frequent emergence of resistant strain is the main problem.

The onset of antimicrobial resistance and subsequent multi-drug resistant organisms significantly increase healthcare-associated expenditure with adverse clinical outcomes.

The present study was undertaken to identify the change in the microbiological flora in the community and nursery of RIMS and their antibiotic susceptibility also comparing the same from our previous study done in 2007-08.

During study period 106 cases of diagnosed newborns were included. Out of this 43 newborn were culture positive. Current study shows predominance of gram positive staphylococcus (8.5%) followed by klebsiella, whereas previous study had shown predominance of gram negative klebsiella (33.3%).

Among the antibiotics studied, maximum overall sensitivity to various organisms is seen with imipenam, piperacillin tazobactam and cefoperazone sulbactam. amikacin and ciprofloxacin and cefotaxim shows moderate sensitivity while ampicillin is resistant to most.

Keywords: Septicaemia, Culture Isolate, Antibiotic Susceptibility, Change In Flora.

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Introduction

Bacterial sepsis is major cause of neonatal morbidity and mortality. A large no. of bacterial and non-bacterial organism causes sepsis during intrauterine, perinatal period or postpartum period. Neonatal bacterial sepsis is characterized by positive blood culture, Raised acute phase reactants with clinical symptoms or signs such as lethargy, respiratory distress, poor feeding or vomiting, abdominal distension, seizures and shock characterized by prolonged capillary refill time. Multiorgan failure and severe shock may be manifestations of severe sepsis.

Neonatal sepsis may be classified as early onset sepsis (EOS), Late onset Sepsis (LOS) or very late onset Sepsis (VLOS). Sepsis presenting within 72 hrs. of life are called Early onset sepsis whereas manifestations after 72 hrs. are called Late onset sepsis In very late onset sepsis, Infection usually comes from community or is acquired during NICU stay but symptoms appear after discharge.

Neonatal infections are estimated to cause about 1.6 million deaths worldwide and 40% of all neonatal deaths due to sepsis occur in developing countries [1].

According to the data from National Neonatal Perinatal Database (NNPD, 2002-03) the incidence of neonatal sepsis is 30 per 1000 live births and sepsis to be one of the commonest causes of neonatal mortality contributing to 19% of all neonatal deaths [2].

The bacteriological profile of neonatal sepsis is constantly under change, more so with advances in early diagnosis, treatment and increased survival of preterm babies. Sepsis, if identified and treated appropriately in time, has very good outcome thus the bacteriological profile needs to be reviewed from time to time [3].

This study was conducted to know the current incidence of sepsis among the babies admitted in our hospital, the pattern of etiological agent in

neonatal sepsis and the antibiotic sensitivity profile of the microorganisms isolated.

So any protocol for sepsis management must be based on the antimicrobial sensitivity, which needs to be reviewed from time to time

Neonatal sepsis is responsible for about 30-50% of total neonatal deaths in developing countries. It is estimated that up to 20% of neonates develop sepsis and approximately 1% die of sepsis related causes [4,5]. Advances in neonatal intensive care have led to improved survival of neonates, but

neonatal sepsis continues to be an important cause of morbidity and mortality.

Aims and Objectives

- To determine the change in the microbiological flora in neonates admitted with neonatal sepsis in Rims nursery.
- To determine the antibiotic susceptibility pattern of the isolated pathogen.
- Compare the present results with previous National and Institutional studies.

METHODOLOGY

SETTING

This study was conducted in the neonatal intensive care unit in the department of paediatrics in Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi from May 2014 to April 2015.

Data collection

106 neonates (aged 0-28 days) clinically suspected of having septicaemia as per the clinical signs and symptoms mentioned in the performa were included in the study. **TABLE 1: Clinical manifestations of neonatal sepsis**

SYMPTOMS	SIGNS
Lethargy Not arousable, comatosed	Respiratory symptoms-
Refusal to suckle	Tachypnea*
Poor cry	Chest retractions*
Hypothermia/Hyperthermia	Grunt*
Abdominal distension	Apnoea/gasping*
Vomiting	
	CNS symptoms
Poor perfusion Shock	Seizures+
Poor weight gain	Blank look+
	High pitched cry+
	Excessive crying/irritability+
	Neck retraction+
	Bulging fontanel+

Prospective observational study with a sample size of 106 neonates (age <28 days) with signs of sepsis.

Criteria of exclusion

The following were excluded from the study

- Neonates with congenital anomalies.
- Acute bilirubin encephalopathy.
- Grade-III perinatal asphyxia.
- Neonates who expired within 24 hrs.
- Neonates with trauma or other surgical problems.

- Neonates on antibiotics or those whose mothers have received antibiotics before delivery

Neonates with features of clinical sepsis were taken after consent from the parents and the following investigations were sent complete blood count with total leucocyte count, absolute neutrophil count, C-reactive protein, band cells, Blood culture and antibiotic sensitivity-cefotaxime, ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, amikacin, piperacillin tazobactam, cefoperazone sulbactam and imipenem.

Data was recorded as per reports and charted in excel sheets and statistical analysis using SSPE software and powerpoint was used for the graphs.

Results

Graph 1: Microbiological profile of blood culture positive cases microbiological profile

1. *Staphylococcus Aureus* - 8.5% [n=9]
2. *Klebsiella* -6.6% [n=7]
3. *Strptococci* -5.7% [n=6],
4. *E coli* - 4.7% [n=5],
5. *Pseudomonas* -3.85 [n=4],
6. *Other Streptococci* -1.9% [n=2] ,
7. *Coagulase Negative Staphylococci* -1.9% [n=2]
8. *Enterobacter* -1.9% [n=2].
9. *Candida* -5.7% [n=6]

Table 1: Organisms isolated in early onset sepsis and late onset sepsis

Organism	Early Onset Sepsis [N]	Late Onset Sepsis [N]
<i>Staphylococcus</i>	3	6
<i>Streptococci</i>	2	4
<i>Klebsiella</i>	5	2
<i>E coli</i>	3	2
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	0	4
<i>Enterobacter</i>	1	1
<i>Other streptococci</i>	1	1
<i>Coagulase negative staphylococci</i>	0	2
<i>Candida</i>	0	6

staphylococcus aureus [n=3]. Other organisms isolated are Streptococci [n=2], Enterobacter [n=1] and Other Streptococci [n=1].

The commonest organism in early onset sepsis is klebsiella [n=5] followed by E coli [n=3] and

Commonest organism in late onset sepsis is staphylococcus aureus [n=6] and Candida [n=6] followed by Streptococci [n=4] and pseudomonas [n=4]. Other organisms isolated are klebsiella[n=2],

E coli[n=2], Coagulase negative staphylococci [n=2], enterobacter[n=1] and other streptococci[n=1].

Graph 2: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of staphylococcus aureus

Staphylococci showed resistance to ampicillin, low sensitivity to cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin and amikacin. High sensitivity to piperacillin tazobactam, cefoperazone sulbactam and imipenam.

Graph 3: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of klebsiella

Klebsiella showed resistance to ampicillin, low sensitivity to cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin and amikacin. High sensitivity to piperacillin tazobactam, cefoperazone sulbactam and imipenam.

Graph 4: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of streptococci

Streptococci showed resistance to ciprofloxacin, low sensitivity to cefotaxime and ampicillin. High sensitivity to piperacillin tazobactam, cefoperazone sulbactam and imipenam.

Graph 5: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of e coli

E coli showed complete resistance to ampicillin and a few cases showed resistance to ciprofloxacin and cefotaxime. High sensitivity to piperacillin tazobactam, cefoperazone sulbactam and imipenam was seen.

Graph 6: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of pseudomonas

Pseudomonas showed complete resistance to ampicillin, low sensitivity to cefotaxime and ciprofloxacin and also to cefoperazone sulbactam. High sensitivity to amikacin, piperacillin tazobactam, and imipenam.

Graph 7: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of other streptococci

Complete resistance to ampicillin is seen. Low sensitivity to piperacillin tazobactam and high sensitivity to cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, cefoperazone sulbactam, amikacin and imipenam was observed.

Graph 8: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of coagulase negative staphylococcus (cons)

Cons showed complete resistance to ampicillin, and high sensitivity to amikacin, ciprofloxacin, piperacillin tazobactam, and imipenam.

Graph 9: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of enterobacter

Some cases of enterobacter showed resistance to cefotaxime, and high sensitivity to ciprofloxacin, cefoperazone sulbactam, piperacillin tazobactam, and imipenam.

Graph 10: Antibiotic sensitivity profile of candida

4 cases out of 6 were sensitive to fluconazole and 5 cases out of 6 were sensitive to amphotericin b.

Graph 11: Sensitivity pattern of antibiotics studied

Among the antibiotics studied, maximum overall sensitivity to various organisms is seen with imipenam, piperacillin tazobactum and cefoperazone sulbactum. Amikacin and ciprofloxacin and cefotaxim shows moderate sensitivity while ampicillin is resistant to most.

Discussion

The present prospective observations were conducted in the department of Pediatrics and Neonatology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi. The selection of cases was done from NICU. 106 cases diagnosed as clinical sepsis

from May 2014 to April 2015 were selected for study.

The bacteriological profile of neonatal sepsis is dynamic with advances in early diagnosis, treatment and increased survival of preterm babies. So it is prudent that protocol for sepsis management must be based on the actual antimicrobial sensitivity, which needs to be reviewed from time to time. The outcome for treatment of sepsis is directly proportional to knowledge of bacteriological profile.

This study was done to know the current microbiological profile of neonatal sepsis among the babies admitted in our hospital, the pattern of etiological agent in neonatal sepsis and the antibiotic sensitivity profile of the microorganisms isolated.

Bacteriological and Microbiological Profile

The gold standard for confirmed diagnosis of sepsis is blood culture. The blood culture positivity rate in our study is 40.50%. In comparison to other studies by Chandra et al [3] (2013), Shah AJ et al [6] (2012), Shaw CK et al., [7] (2007) and Bhattacharjee et al., [8] were 37.63%, 31.75%, 54.64%, and 32% respectively.

The commonest organism identified in our study was staphylococcus aureus (8.5%) [n=9] which is very similar to recent study by Chandra et al 6 and Shaw CK et al.,[7]

The other gram positive organisms to be isolated in the current study were streptococcal species and coagulase negative staphylococcus.

The second most common organism and commonest among gram negative organism found was klebsiella (6.6%) [n=7] as was also seen by Shaw CK et al [7]

Other gram negative organisms found were E coli(4.7%)[n=5], pseudomonas (3.8%)[n=4] and enterobacter(1.9%)[n=2].

The study carried out in Rajendra institute of medical sciences, Ranchi by Verma et al from 1st may 2007 to 30th June 2008 also showed klebsiella spp to be the commonest 33.33 % followed by staphylococcus 24.07%, E coli 11.11 % and pseudomonas 7.41 %.

Thus the presence of staphylococci as the commonest organism in current study shows a change in the earlier bacteriological profile in the institute.

Among the isolates Candida species were found to have a rate of 5.7% (n=6). All of them isolated only in late onset sepsis group.

In our study, most of the isolates were resistant to penicillin. Ampicillin, cefotaxim & ciprofloxacin

had lowest sensitivity to the bacterial isolates. Highest sensitivity was recorded with piperacillin tazobactam and imipenam followed by amikacin and cefoperazone sulbactam. Imipenam showed sensitivity of 100%. Low sensitivity of commonly used antibiotics and fair sensitivity to amikacin was also observed by other authors. Tallur et al4 showed that most isolates were resistant to ampicillin, gentamicin and cotrimoxazole.

Summary

Current study includes 106 cases of neonatal sepsis. Prospective observational study was conducted. Neonates with clinical sepsis were selected as per criteria and laboratory investigations were performed as per protocol. The following observations were made.

- Male to female ratio was 0.9. There is a slight female preponderance.
- Out born neonate (55%) were higher in number than the inborn (45%) with neonatal sepsis.
- Late onset sepsis (75.5%) was more common than early onset sepsis.
- Almost all the neonatal groups showed preponderance of late onset sepsis(n=77) with highest percentage in low birth weight babies.
- Blood culture was positive in 40.6% of cases.
- CSF culture was done in a few patients but none showed any growth. This might be related to unregulated antibiotic misuse.
- Blood culture showed staphylococcus aureus (8.5%) [n=9] to be the commonest organism isolated.
- Second most common organism was klebsiella (6.6%)[n=7] followed by Streptococci (5.7%)[n=6], E coli (4.7%)[n=5], pseudomonas (3.8) [n=4], Other Streptococci (1.9%)[n=2], Coagulase negative staphylococci (1.9%)[n=2] and Enterobacter (1.9%)[n=2].
- Candida spp was found in 5.7% [n=6] of cases. All Candida positive cultures were of neonates with late onset sepsis.
- The commonest organism in early onset sepsis is klebsiella [n=5] followed by E coli [n=3] and staphylococcus aureus [n=3]. Other organisms isolated are Streptococci [n=2], Enterobacter [n=1] and Other Streptococci [n=1].
- Commonest organism in late onset sepsis is staphylococcus aureus [n=6] and Candida [n=6] followed by Streptococci [n=4] and pseudomonas [n=4]. Other organisms isolated are klebsiella[n=2], E coli[n=2], Coagulase negative staphylococci [n=2], enterobacter[n=1] and other streptococci[n=1].

- Most of the bacterial isolates showed resistance to penicillin and other first line drugs used in empirical therapy.
- Ampicillin, cefotaxim & ciprofloxacin had lowest sensitivity to the bacterial isolates. Highest sensitivity was recorded with piperacillin tazobactam and imipenam followed by amikacin and cefoperazone sulbactam.
- *Candida* sp. was more sensitive to amphotericin B than to fluconazole, though some cases resistant to amphotericin B and sensitive to fluconazole was also seen.

Conclusion and Recommendation

- Neonatal sepsis is a leading cause of neonatal admissions, morbidity and mortality in developing countries. Bacterial spectrum for sepsis could be different in different regions. Sensitivity pattern also differs accordingly.
- The antibiotic susceptibility pattern in our study suggested that, initial empirical choice of piperacillin tazobactam in combination with amikacin was the most appropriate as maximum isolates were sensitive to either piperacillin tazobactam or amikacin.
- A low susceptibility to commonly used antibiotics like ampicillin and cefotaxim is a cause for concern.
- The knowledge of prevailing strains and the antibiotic sensitivity patterns in the region is mandatory for each centre due to temporal changes in the causative organisms and their antibiotic susceptibility.
- Periodic evaluations not only reveals the recent trend of increasing resistance to commonly used antibiotics but also helps in implementation of a rational empirical therapy.
- The increasing resistance to antibiotics are a rising concern and we need to look into the matter and implement strategies to prevent both early onset sepsis and late onset sepsis.

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